

Mapping Media for Future Democracies

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DELIVERABLE 6.3

Blog on citizens' parliaments

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Executive Summary

A blog on the Citizens' Parliaments on Media and Democracy

Deliverable D.6.3 is a public blog on the citizens' parliaments (CP) on Media and democracy, implemented by the WP6 partners, COMMIT, CU, MI, and MIC in their respective countries, Austria, the Czech Republic, Slovenia, and Ireland.

The name of the blog is *MeDeMAP Blog* and its internet address is: <https://medemap.commit.at/medemap-blog/>

In Work Package 6, "Supply meets demand", citizens are involved in the MeDeMAP research project, which follows a participatory action research approach. Between March and May 2025, twenty citizens from Austria, the Czech Republic, Ireland, and Slovenia took part in four Citizens' Parliaments organised by COMMIT, CU, MI and MIC. These parliaments were designed in accordance with the specifications set out in Deliverable D6.2, and the participants learned, deliberated and adopted resolutions on media and democracy.

The *MeDeMAP Blog* has accompanied the implementation of the Citizens' Parliaments from their launch to the presentation of their results at the national level.

A blog managed by COMMIT with contributions from each partner

COMMIT set up the blog in September 2024. The *MeDeMAP Blog* is organised as an English-language subsection of a website that also has a German-language section dedicated exclusively to the Austrian CP. The posts are illustrated with pictures taken during the sessions.

Each WP6 partner has published contributions to announce the launch of its CP, report on each four sessions dedicated to a specific topic (Media and democracy, Media systems and regulation, representation in the media, participation in and through the media) and on its national presentation of the CP's results. CU, MI and COMMIT have already published a final comment.

The blog is still open to allow for additional contributions. Reports on these forthcoming events are already planned: the national presentation of the Irish CP's results, the roundtable on the CPs' experiences, organised by COMMIT within the MeDeMAP Project Meeting in September 2025 and the presentation of all 4 CPs in the European Parliament in early 2026.

In addition to the *MeDeMAP Blog*, COMMIT has also published and will publish further blog posts about the CPs on the Electronic Platform for Adult Learning in Europe, EPAL, which are addressed to the European community engaged in adult education.

Zooming in on the content of the blog posts

The *MeDeMAP Blog* is public. It is aimed at the general public of the WP6 partner countries and at CP participants in particular, as well as at stakeholders from the media, politics and civil society organisations. The Blog is intended to inform on the purpose, the organization, the process (learning, deliberation, adoption) and the outcomes of the CPs.

By 4 August 2025, the WP6 partners have published 28 blog posts on the *MeDeMAP Blog*. Two more posts will be published in autumn, reporting on the national presentation of the Irish CP and the roundtable on the WP6 experience with the CPs, and another blog post will be published until February 2026 on the European presentation of the CPs in the European Parliament.

The blog posts follow guidelines concerning their format and structure as set out in Deliverable D6.2. Blog posts should be between 1500 and 3500 signs, contain at least two photos with credits, and follow the structure of title, lead and paragraphs with subtitles.

The first series of blog posts, published from October 2024 to March 2025, introduced the upcoming citizens' parliaments, their objectives, and their role within the MeDeMAP research project. They also served as a recruitment call for participants.

In a second wave, the WP6 partners reported on their opening session, during which the main topic of 'Media and Democracy' was introduced. The posts covered the day's process, including the learning phase with experts, the facilitated discussions, the decision-making process and the results: On day one, participants created a list of subtopics for the following sessions.

The third, fourth, and fifth waves of blog posts documented day 2, 3 and 4 on Media systems and regulation, Representation in the media, Participation in and through the media respectively, presenting the process and the resolutions adopted during the sessions. Each WP6 partner underlined the focus of its resolutions. For example, media responsibility was one focus of the third session of the Slovenian CP on representation. In their reports, the WP6 partners also described and quoted the main takeaway from the expert inputs, as well as the collaboration between participants and their reactions. Posts on the last CP sessions also summarize the achievements and provide information on the coming national presentations.

In June, in a sixth wave of posts, COMMIT, CU and MI reported on their national presentations of their CP's results with a link to the English version of their national report. MIC will hold its national presentation in the autumn and report on it in an upcoming blog post.

Additionally, COMMIT, CU and MI have already published final reflections on their CPs and the resolutions adopted.

In addition to the posts published on the *MeDeMAP Blog*, COMMIT has begun to post Blog Posts on the CPs on the Electronic Platform for Adult Learning in Europe, EPAL, which are addressed to the European community engaged in adult education.¹

¹ On the EPAL Platform, the following blog post can already be found: "Citizens' Parliaments as participatory learning spaces for democracy education" (28.03.2025), <https://epale.ec.europa.eu/en/blog/citizens-parliaments-participatory-learning-spaces-democracy-education>

Some indicative statistics on the blog

The blog was set up using WordPress, and the Matomo analytics tool was integrated to analyze usage. This tool is specifically designed to protect user privacy and only evaluates immediate data on access numbers. The visits and page view data relate to the entire website, including the English WP6 blog posts and the COMMIT posts in German on the Austrian CP.

From 1.10.2024 to 31.7.2025:

- 3556 visits
- 8845 page views
- Average time per visit: 2 minutes 54 seconds
- 2.6 actions per visit (e.g. page viewing, downloading, research)
- Visits mainly via the blog address (2651 or 74%), other websites (11%), search engines (10%), and social media (5%).

COMMIT has widely advertised the blog in Austria before, between and after the CPs' sessions, at events and presentations, and on flyers and other printed materials. This explains the importance of direct access (74%). 11% of visits originated from other websites, including partners' and media websites.

List of blog posts published on the MeDeMAP Blog on Citizens' Parliaments by partner and date

COMMIT

- 02.10.2024. Post announcing WP6 CPs and their articulation within MeDeMAP research project.

Citizens' Parliaments Media and Democracy in Austria, Ireland, Slovenia and the Czech Republic.

<https://medemap.commit.at/citizens-parliaments-media-and-democracy-in-austria-ireland-slovenia-and-the-czech-republic/>

- 11.03.2025. Announcing the launch of the four CPs in March

Introducing: Citizens' Parliaments Media and Democracy in Austria, Ireland, Slovenia and the Czech

Republic. <https://medemap.commit.at/introducing-citizens-parliaments-media-and-democracy-in-austria-ireland-slovenia-and-the-czech-republic/>

- 17.03.2025. Kick off CP in Austria

The Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy starts on 22 March.

<https://medemap.commit.at/the-austrian-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-starts-on-22-march/>

- 27.03.2025. Report on CP1 in Austria

Quality, transparency, and media literacy: At the first meeting of the Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy in Austria, participants identify key issues. <https://medemap.commit.at/quality-transparency-and-media-literacy-at-the-first-meeting-of-the-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-in-austria-participants-identify-key-issues/>

- 10.04.2025. Report on CP2 in Austria

Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy adopts 19 resolutions on the media system and media regulation. <https://medemap.commit.at/austrian-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-adopts-19-resolutions-on-the-media-system-and-media-regulation/>

- 30.04.2025. Report on CP3 in Austria

Austrian Citizens adopt 19 resolutions on participation in and through the media.

<https://medemap.commit.at/austrian-citizens-adopt-19-resolutions-on-participation-in-and-through-the-media/>

- 21.05.2025. Report on CP4 in Austria

The Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy in Austria held its final meeting. Political stakeholders and the media are called to take action. <https://medemap.commit.at/the-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-in-austria-held-its-final-meeting-political-stakeholders-and-the-media-are-called-to-take-action/>

- 30.06.2025. Report on the national presentation of the CP's results in Austria

The Austrian Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy presents its demands.

<https://medemap.commit.at/the-austrian-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-presents-its-demands/>

- 04.08.2025. Final reflections on CP Austria

Short reflections on the Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy in Austria.

<https://medemap.commit.at/short-reflections-on-the-citizen-parliament-media-and-democracy-in-austria/>

CU

- 11.03.2025. Kick off CP in the Czech Republic

The Czech Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy will start in Prague on 15 March

<https://medemap.commit.at/czech-citizens-parliament-media-and-democracy-start/>

- 24.03.2025. Report on CP1 Czech Republic

Czech citizens deliberated about how to strengthen the multiple voices of media audiences.

<https://medemap.commit.at/czech-citizens-deliberated-about-how-to-strengthen-the-multiple-voices-of-media-audiences/>

- 11.04.2025. Report on CP2 Czech Republic

Support community media and improve conditions for journalists. Czech Citizens' Parliament adopted the first resolutions. <https://medemap.commit.at/support-community-media-and-improve-conditions-for-journalists-czech-citizens-parliament-adopted-the-first-resolutions/>

- 06.05.2025. Report on CP3 Czech Republic

Czech citizens formulate nine resolutions for pluralist and inclusive media representations.

<https://medemap.commit.at/czech-citizens-adopt-nine-resolutions-for-pluralist-and-inclusive-media-representations/>

- 10.06.2025. Report on CP4 Czech Republic

The Czech citizen parliament concludes its sessions with demands for enhancing citizen participation in and through the media. <https://medemap.commit.at/the-czech-citizen-parliament-concludes-its-sessions-with-demands-for-enhancing-citizen-participation-in-and-through-the-media/>

- 16.06.2025. Report on the national presentation of the CP's results in the Czech Republic

The Czech Citizen Parliament on Media and Democracy submits its resolutions to the Senate of the Czech Republic. <https://medemap.commit.at/the-czech-citizen-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-submits-its-resolutions-to-the-senate-of-the-czech-republic/>

- 20.06.2025. Final reflection on CP Czech Republic

A final reflection about the Czech citizen parliament on media and democracy.

<https://medemap.commit.at/a-final-reflection-about-the-czech-citizen-parliament-on-media-and-democracy/>

MI

- 12.03.2025. Kick off CP Slovenia

Kicking off the first citizens' parliament on media and democracy in Slovenia.

<https://medemap.commit.at/kicking-off-the-first-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-in-slovenia/>

- 21.03.2025. Report on CP1 Slovenia

„Challenges for citizens to navigate the complex media environment”. First Citizens’ Parliament on media and democracy in Slovenia addresses key issues. <https://medemap.commit.at/challenges-for-citizens-to-navigate-the-complex-media-environment-first-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-in-slovenia-addresses-key-issues/>

- 03.04.2025. Report on CP2 Slovenia

From media economy to systemic reform: Second Citizens’ Parliament in Slovenia unveils first 11 demands. <https://medemap.commit.at/from-media-economy-to-systemic-reform-second-citizens-parliament-in-slovenia-unveils-first-11-demands/>

- 21.04.2025. Report on CP3 Slovenia

Citizens’ Parliament in Slovenia continues the discussion: representation, media responsibility, and 12 new demands. <https://medemap.commit.at/citizens-parliament-in-slovenia-continues-the-discussion-representation-media-responsibility-and-12-new-demands/>

- 14.05.2025. Report on CP4 Slovenia

The people have spoken – now what? The citizens’ parliament on media and democracy in Slovenia may have ended but the process is just beginning. <https://medemap.commit.at/the-people-have-spoken-now-what-the-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-in-slovenia-may-have-ended-but-the-process-is-just-beginning/>

- 10.06.2025. Report on the national presentation of the CP's results in Slovenia

Public presentation of Slovenian Citizens’ Parliament demands. <https://medemap.commit.at/public-presentation-of-slovenian-citizens-parliament-demands/>

- 04.07.2025. Summary of Resolutions of Slovenian CP

Summary of the Citizens’ Parliament demands (resolutions) in Slovenia. <https://medemap.commit.at/summary-of-the-citizens-parliament-demands-resolutions-in-slovenia/>

MIC

- 19.03.2025. Kick off CP Ireland

Media and Democracy – Citizens have their say. Citizens’ Parliament starts in Ireland. <https://medemap.commit.at/media-and-democracy-citizens-have-their-say-citizens-parliament-starts-in-ireland/>

- 01.04.2025. Report on CP1 Ireland

The National Citizens’ Parliament on Media and Democracy in Ireland met for the first time on Saturday 22nd March in Mary Immaculate College, Limerick. <https://medemap.commit.at/the-national-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-in-ireland-met-for-the-first-time-on-saturday-22nd-march-in-mary-immaculate-college-limerick/>

- 09.04.2025. Report on CP2 Ireland

Irish Citizens’ Parliament on Media and Democracy halfway there. <https://medemap.commit.at/irish-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-halfway-there/>

- 02.05.2025. Report on CP3 Ireland

Irish Citizens' Parliament on Media and Democracy adopts 10 resolutions on media systems and representation in the media. <https://medemap.commit.at/irish-citizens-parliament-on-media-and-democracy-adopts-10-resolutions-on-media-systems-and-representation-in-the-media/>

- 14.05.2025. Report on CP4 Ireland

Irish national Citizens' Parliament finishes on a high note. <https://medemap.commit.at/irish-national-citizens-parliament-finishes-on-a-high-note/>